

CS - MACH1

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (v1)

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List of referenced acronyms

AUAF	American University of Armenia Foundation
CARE	Collective benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CROPS	Curating, Replicating, Orchestrating, and Propagating Citizen Science across Europe
CS	Citizen Science
CS-MACHI	MARine Citizen science data Horizon
DG MARE	The Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
DG RTD	The Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTO	Digital Twin Ocean
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EDITO	European Digital Twin Ocean
EGU	European Geosciences Union
EMD	European Maritime Day
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EO	Expected Outcome
EOOS	European Ocean Observing System
ETT	ETT S.p.A., Deda Group
EU	European Union
EurOBIS	European node of the Ocean Biodiversity Information System
EuroGOOS	European Global Ocean Observing System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
ICM-CSIC	Institut de Ciències del Mar - Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
ICMBO	International Conference on Marine Biology and Oceanography
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
Ifremer	French Institute for Ocean Science
IMPETUS4CS	Impetus for Citizen Science Project
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LandSeaLot	Land-Sea Interface: Let's Observe Together
MARIS	Marine Information Service, MARIS B.V.
MCS	Marine Citizen Science
MCSDN	Marine Citizen Science Data Network
MCSI	Marine Citizen Science Initiatives
MSP	Maritime Spatial Planning
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NOC-BODC	National Oceanography Center - British Oceanographic Data Centre
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices System

OSM	Ocean Sciences Meeting
OTTERS	Social Transformation for Water Stewardship through Scaling Up Citizen Science
OutBe	OutBe S.R.L.
SCOOP	Solutions for Cost-effective Ocean Observation Platform
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SeaDataNet	Pan-European infrastructure for ocean & marine data management
SME	Small and Medium Sized Enterprise
SMHI	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
SO	Specific Objective
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
TG	Target Group
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focused, Sustainability, and Technology
UM	University of Malta
UN	United Nations
VLIZ	Flanders Marine Institute
WCMB	World Conference on Marine Biodiversity
WP	Work Package

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Summary

This document encompasses the first version of the CS-MACH1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan, and specifies the communication, exploitation and dissemination strategy and activities that CS-MACH1 will undertake, particularly in the first 18 months of the project. After this period the document will be revised and updated as version 2 (D6.2) and a final version 3 (D6.3).

The plan aims to increase CS-MACH1's impact across all the work packages by raising awareness, promoting participation and making sure that the results and outputs reach the target stakeholder groups. The plan includes the objectives (why), target stakeholder groups (who), key messages (what), the planned phases and timing of communication, dissemination and exploitation actions (when), the tools and materials used (how), and the channels through which the project will communicate and disseminate results (where), together with key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor progress. A post-project plan is also included, supporting continued dissemination and exploitation of results after the project ends.

1. Preamble (About this document)

The CS-MACH1 CDE Plan outlines how the project will maximise its reach and long-term impact by engaging a wide range of stakeholders and ensuring participation across educational, societal, and scientific sectors. It aims to refine and target specific audiences, promote CS-MACH1's findings, resources, and interlinked directory, and facilitate knowledge transfer across citizen, policy, and research communities. For this, it describes specific dissemination, exploitation and communication activities that are to be implemented throughout the project.

The approach is structured around core dimensions: the objectives (why), target stakeholder groups (who), key messages (what), the planned phases and timing of communication, dissemination and exploitation actions (when), the tools and materials used (how), and the channels through which actions are communication and dissemination are actioned (where).

Furthermore, monitoring the effectiveness and impact of all activities planned in this document will be guided by defined key performance indicators (KPIs), aligned with the CS-MACH1 objectives and expected results.

The CDE Plan is a living document and will be further developed in Deliverables D6.2 and D6.3, due in M18 and M28 respectively. Each subsequent version will include reporting of completed activities and an assessment of their effectiveness against KPIs. The versions D6.2 and D6.3 will additionally include a greater emphasis on dissemination and exploitation activities as CS-MACH1 project results are progressively delivered, with project communication continuing throughout all versions.

2. Context: CS-MACH1

2.1 About the project

Marine citizen science (MCS) holds significant potential as a great source of marine data worldwide. However, in the current MSC landscape there are often different protocols and tools used for the collection and management of the data, and training of marine citizen scientists. This leads to difficulties to streamline all the incoming data; data gets lost and is not as accessible, or trusted by the scientific community, thereby losing value. CS-MACH1 will, over a period of 30 months, create a marine-data network that builds on existing knowledge and infrastructures. The network will provide access to best practices for deployment and data management, training material about and for MCS communities, initiatives and projects, and will showcase the use of affordable, durable, and user-friendly marine observation devices suitable for citizen science in different marine environments. This network, the Marine Citizen Science Data Network (MCSDN), will act as a platform bringing marine citizen science initiatives (MSCI), marine data management experts, cost-efficient technology providers and marine scientists together. It will connect with existing infrastructure content of the European Citizen Science Platform and the Solutions for Cost-effective Ocean Observation Platform (SCOOP), recently endorsed as a project of the UN Ocean Decade programme CoastPredict. By bringing together European MCS actors, CS-MACH1 aims to facilitate improved management, sharing, quality control and standardisation of their data, enhance citizen engagement in MCS initiatives, and better integrate marine citizen science data with major services or initiatives such as EMODnet, the European Digital Twin of the Ocean, and others. To ensure engagement and participation, CS-MACH1 will support continuous interaction between citizen science (CS) communities, technology providers, data management experts and researchers, and provide the necessary cost-efficient technology, data management best practices and standards, training and support to produce findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR) data flows.

2.2 Specific objectives, expected outcomes, expected impacts and key exploitable results of the project

Communication, outreach and dissemination strategies are planned to contribute to, support and promote CS-MACH1's specific objectives, expected outcomes and key exploitable results.

Activities detailed in this plan will support achievement of CS-MACH1's objectives and expected outcomes, disseminate the project's results, and support their exploitation during and after the project period.

2.2.1 Specific objectives

CS-MACH1's specific objectives are defined as:

SO 1 Building a pan-EU Marine Citizen Science Data Network between relevant initiatives, including existing CS initiatives, cost-efficient technology developers, data management experts, and the potential end-users of the data such as scientists and policy makers. This will be supported by an online directory providing access to all materials and output.

SO 2 Support the development of data management standards, technologies and best practices to support the dataflow of MCS programmes, ensuring their data can be adopted by end-users.

SO 3 Enable and demonstrate enhanced FAIRness of the CS (meta)data, ensuring it can feed into international data infrastructures such as EMODnet, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS and GEOSS, and onwards to DTO.

SO 4 Maximise the data uptake and impact by developing training materials and toolkits that prepare CS initiatives for upscaling and integration with end users such as the scientific community and in line with the EU data infrastructures requirements.

SO 5 Demonstrate the full potential of CS observation data through real-world use-cases, using cost-efficient devices, elevate CS concepts, and showcase how resulting dataflows can be transformed into valuable data products.

SO 6 Communicate the developed CS data approach and define a long term sustainability strategy for the network, by communicating and sharing MCS data, best practices and other results of the project with diverse communities and the wider audience, as well as creating a fit-for-purpose sustainability plan to ensure the network's future.

2.2.2 Expected outcomes

CS-MACH1's expected outcomes are defined as:

EO 1: Establishment of a pan-European Marine Citizen Science Data Network, bringing together actors of MCS around Europe and in neighboring countries.

EO 2: Harmonise MSC data and methods to increase the added value of the MCS activities, adaptation of data and metadata standards and methodological approaches appropriate for use in MCS based on the existing European frameworks, as developed by SeaDataNet, EMODnet and other marine data infrastructures.

EO 3: Increased visibility and impact of MCS activities in Europe.

EO 4: Sharing of good practices on MCS information and data consumption.

EO 5: Deployment of cost-efficient, CS appropriate observing equipment.

2.2.3 Expected impacts

The expected impacts of CS-MACH1 are outlined below, highlighting how the project outcome will benefit stakeholders and deliver meaningful contributions to science, society and policy.

Expected impact 1: Increase the added value coming from MCS by ensuring that the information and data they collect becomes available and useful for wider use. This will mainly be achieved by elevating the efforts of citizen scientists and improving the FAIRness of their data.

Expected impact 2: Support targeted engagement of different categories of social actors in the production of credible Marine Knowledge, to support the development of the Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System. CS-MACH1 connects and engages a network of MCS actors to encourage marine observation and data collection, and demonstrate how this data can be used in the DTO via specific use cases.

Expected impact 3: Supporting the scaling up of MCS activities in Europe. Through training activities, demonstration use cases, and the creation of a directory to support and highlight impactful MCSI, CS-MACH1 engages MCS actors, fosters collaboration, and informs policy-making, laying the foundation for a sustainable MCS network beyond the project's duration.

2.2.4 Key exploitable results (KERs)

The project will develop five Key Exploitable Results (KERs), which will be leveraged both during and beyond CS-MACH1's lifetime. These KERs are directly aligned with and support the specific objectives outlined above.

Table 1. CS-MACH1 KERs

	SO1	SO2	SO3	SO4	SO5	SO6
KER1: Marine Citizen Science Data Network	X					
KER2: Project website in the form of a Web Directory, hosting all resources generated and directory links in the context of CS-MACH1, maintained for at least seven years including	X					X
KER2.1: Links to the main MCS projects, sensors and data repositories	X	X				
KER2.2: Protocols and guidelines for MCS data FAIRness		X	X			
KER2.3: Training materials and protocols for deployment of cost-efficient sensors				X		
KER2.4: Policy briefs and recommendations				X		
KER3: Training in pilot sites - Skills acquired				X	X	
KER4: Lessons learnt (post co-design and use-cases) from end users/stakeholders				X	X	
KER5: CS-MACH1 roadmap - Roadmap to guide transitioning from project completion to 'beyond-the-project' follow-up actions, including the sustainability of the network and directory						X

3. Aims and Objectives of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (why)

Effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation of project results are essential requirements under Horizon Europe funding. These activities are critical to ensure that the knowledge, tools, and outcomes generated achieve broad visibility, relevance, and lasting impact beyond the project's lifetime.

This document includes plans for CS-MACH1 communication, dissemination and exploitation together. It is important to make clear distinction between these activities for clear and effective planning.

- **Communication** aims to inform, promote and communicate project activities and results.
- **Dissemination** aims to make the knowledge and results generated by the project publicly available free-of-charge.
- **Exploitation** aims to make concrete use of project results (KERs) for commercial, societal or political purposes.

The general objectives of CS-MACH1’s communication, dissemination and exploitation are:

- To effectively communicate, disseminate and multiply the project activities, opportunities and results to the related CS projects actors of the different target groups (e.g. divers, fishermen, leisure sailors, tourists, blue economy actors, developers of cost-effective instruments and monitoring equipment) and through the consortium networks and connections to a broad and diverse audience.
- To attract and empower a large number of MCS actors for the data integration in EMODnet and accessibility by EU DTO;
- To develop the project legacy and a roadmap for sustainability of the project outcomes

To maximise the impact of the project, this CDE Plan is designed to detail the project target groups, key messages and communication channels, outline how dissemination, exploitation and communication can support the sustainability of the outputs and their continued uptake by the CS community.

Specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for communication activities and other project outputs relevant to the project’s expected impacts are detailed in Section 9: tracking and performance monitoring.

4. Target stakeholder groups (who)

Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities aim to engage a broad and diverse audience, facilitating participation across educational, societal, and scientific sectors. To maximise impact, refined target groups have been identified to ensure that CS-MACH1’s findings, resources, and interlinked directory effectively promote knowledge transfer between citizens, policymakers, and the research community. Given the diversity of marine citizen science actions, communication materials and resources will be carefully tailored to the needs and expectations of each target group, as outlined in Table 2 below.

Table 2. CS-MACH1 target stakeholder groups

Target Group	Stakeholder description	C & D objectives	Relevance and description
TG1: Academia	The marine and social science research community: Academic and research institutions, especially focused on CS and the oceanographic sciences	To share project results and methodologies with, promoting the usage of CS derived data in marine research	By showcasing citizen science initiatives that apply optimal methodologies, follow best practices, and generate data of high quality and standard, CS-MACH1 seeks to build trust in CS data within the academic community

TG2: Wider civil society	All potential communities of citizen scientists: e.g. diving & outdoor centers, sailing teams, recreational fishing communities, tourists, (Blue) schools	To involve in data collection through CS, training and the pilot projects	Key players in CS-MACH1. They contribute data and provide use cases—supported through training and workshops—to demonstrate reliable data flows and information into robust ocean data infrastructures
TG3: CS projects and communities representatives	CS coordinators, researchers and related societal actors: All groups' coordinators associated with CS	To engage in MCS through the CS-MACH1 approach and to share the project format to elevate the value and uptake of data	This group plays a crucial role by guiding CS initiatives toward best practices, enabling high-quality data collection and ensuring effective data integration
TG4: Boundary organisations	NGOs, foundations, local governmental entities: Local cultural groups & society linking the dots	To facilitate the local knowledge transfer and training from CS coordinators to civil groups	This group plays a key role in connecting local CSI, amplifying CS-MACH1's objectives, and demonstrating project methodologies in practice
TG5: IT industry	Industries, SME, coordinators, and IT research institutions: IT manufacturers, sensors developers	To accelerate development and promote usage of low-cost technologies for participatory marine monitoring	Technology developers are essential partners, providing the cost-effective tools and innovations that empower CSI to expand marine observations and generate data ready for integration into ocean data infrastructures
TG6: Policy makers and media	Industry, environmental, societal, and public bodies: Media agencies and governmental services related to the relevant EU mission	To present the benefits and results of the CS-MACH1 approach and of CS in marine research and monitoring	This group is key for amplifying CS-MACH1's impact, helping disseminate results, and showcasing how CS contributes to marine research, monitoring, and EU Mission Ocean objectives
TG7: EU Ocean and CS transnational networks	EU, Related Mission Projects, European networks and resources platforms: e.g. BlueCloud, LandSeaLot, Prep4Blue, ProBleu, CROPS, OTTERS, Ocean Literacy portal, Eu-citizen.science platform and other EU	To sustain the project resources and framework beyond its lifetime, while identifying suitable partners	Existing CS network and programmes are crucial for ensuring CS-MACH1's post-project legacy and its continued impact on marine research and monitoring

	and international programmes and networks		
TG8: Larger scale data platforms	Regional, national, EU and global; endorsed and established: Data repositories/modelling platforms (e.g.EMODnet, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, CMEMS, CoastPredict, EDITO), data managers	To promote and standardise the uptake of CS derived data in marine monitoring and modelling	This group is an essential component in CS-MACH1, enabling the standardisation, integration, and broad-scale use of CS-derived data within robust marine data infrastructures

5. Key messages (what)

The table below summarises the overarching key messages to be communicated from CS-MACH1. These key messages are pertinent to particular target groups, described above. More specific and detailed messaging will be developed throughout the project as tasks develop and the needs of specific target groups are refined.

Table 3. CS-MACH1 key messages for each target stakeholder group

Key message	Target group
CS-MACH1 increases the impact of marine citizen science initiatives and the value of the data they produce.	All
CS-MACH1 supports marine citizen science initiatives and their data management, unlocking an enormous amount of so far untapped marine data that will become available to and trusted by all users as a result.	All
The Marine Citizen Science Data Network (MCSDN) will connect European marine citizen science actors to facilitate improved management, sharing, quality control and standardisation of their data, enhance citizen engagement in marine citizen science initiatives, and better integrate marine citizen science data with major services or initiatives such as EMODnet, the European Digital Twin of the Ocean, and others.	All
Affordable, durable, and user-friendly marine observation devices, suitable for citizen science initiatives, can produce high quality data and contribute to increased marine data provision to key operational services.	TG1, TG2 TG3, TG4, TG7, TG8
CS-MACH1 training materials support marine citizen science initiatives to empower new and experienced citizen scientists to collect, manage and share data more effectively.	All

CS-MACH1 data and observation protocols ensure citizen science data quality quantification and quality control, improving its usability and credibility for different stakeholders.	TG1, TG2, TG3, TG5, TG7, TG8
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6. Communication, dissemination and exploitation campaigns (when)

CS-MACH1 communication, dissemination and exploitation will be divided into three distinct phases, each with a different emphasis based on the stage of the project and results/outcomes delivered. These three campaigns will align with and be guided by the three versions of this plan: v1 (D6.1, M6), v2 (D6.2, M18) and v3 (D6.3, M28). Campaign one continues throughout the whole project, overlapping with campaigns two and three. A detailed content plan for the project’s communication, dissemination and exploitation campaigns will be developed internally, and serve as a living document to guide day-to-day activities within the campaigns.

6.1 Campaign one (M1-30) - Awareness and promotion (predominantly communication activities)

Purpose: To raise awareness and visibility of CS-MACH1 and its objectives with all stakeholder groups.

Communication and dissemination material will be produced to introduce the project and highlight its activities to all target groups. This campaign will run throughout the entire project. Planned highlights for the first eighteen months are indicated below. Others will be added as the project progresses. This phase includes highlighting news, activities and outputs, from CS-MACH1, as well as activities in the wider landscape in which CS-MACH1 sits.

In this first phase, we will build CS-MACH1’s community of stakeholders. We will do it online using the project’s communication channels (website, social media) backed up by the consortium partners that will support and amplify the project’s communication efforts.

Planned communication highlights supporting Phase 1:

- CS-MACH1 kicks-off
- Get to know CS-MACH1, its partners, objectives and upcoming activities
- The need for a Marine Citizen Science Data Network
- Meet MCSDN members and data providers
- Social media launch
- Website launch
- Project’s news and events (shared on the website and social media, and by our consortium partners)
- Newsletter subscription campaign
- Release of CS-MACH1’s newsletter

6.2 Campaign two (M18- 27) - Outreach & Engagement (Communication and dissemination equal)

Purpose: To promote active engagement with CS-MACH1 opportunities (MCSDN).

This campaign will focus on targeting stakeholders with specific 'calls to action' to mobilise their involvement with CS-MACH1 activities. A significant focus of this campaign will be to identify and recruit members of the MCSDN. As such, the most important target groups for this phase will be TGs 2 and 3. This campaign will also highlight the CS-MACH1 training opportunities.

Planned highlights supporting Phase 2:

- Launch of the MCSDN, call for members
- Join CS-MACH1 training activities
- Dissemination on social media, website, newsletter and exploitation of consortium partners' memberships and connections
- Creation of *ad hoc* messages and communication materials for our audiences
- Social media campaigns tailored for the project's target audiences

6.3 Campaign three (M28-30 and post project) - Uptake (Dissemination and exploitation, post-project planning)

Purpose: To disseminate CS-MACH1 key exploitable results (KER) and outputs (deliverables, factsheets, infographics, training webinars, data flows and products) to the relevant stakeholder groups who can exploit them.

Planned highlights supporting Phase 3:

- Activation of the online and offline stakeholder communities built in phase 1 and expanded in phase 2
- Dissemination throughout the project's communication channels (website, social media, newsletter, in-person events, scientific papers and conferences) supported by partners' networks
- Dissemination using EU channels and platforms (e.g. European Citizen Science Platform)

All phases will be supported by planned and targeted content shared via the various channels (described further below).

7. Tools and materials (how)

7.1 Visual identity and branding materials

CS-MACH1 visual identity, logo and branding materials were co-designed in a **participatory** way involving all consortium partners. A questionnaire was circulated to gather input from all partners to the visual identity and an extended interactive discussion was held during the kick off meeting to reach a collective consensus on the project's branding.

The resulting CS-MACHI branding aims to communicate the project as **engaging, inclusive, trustworthy, and collaborative**, avoiding overly formal tones. The visual identity emphasises symbols of **connection, data flow, marine tools, and people**, with a strong alignment to **EMODnet** and EU Mission Ocean palettes but avoiding generic “blue-only” institutional visuals or often used ocean imagery. The branding aims to be **simple, modern and minimalist, with a flat 2D style**, allowing optimal adaptability and easy implementation in different contexts.

Full details of the project branding, including different versions of the logo and guidelines for use, are included in Annexe 1.

7.1.1 Project logo

Developed following the partners’ feedback that was given during the kick-off meeting activity, the finalised logo (Fig. 1) draws from the **waves** and the **concept of speed**, while also introducing a human element to emphasise the **central role of people** within the project. The logo design aligns with the project’s focus on **data, networks, and accessibility**, where focus is placed on the individuals who enable the **convergence of data** and the activation and management of projects. Its shapes suggest connection and flow, symbolising the way CS-MACHI brings together diverse marine citizen science actors to accelerate data sharing. The waves and the colour palette evoke the **marine environment**, contrasting with the lime yellow used in broader visual identity as a distinctive element.

The logo pictogram can be easily separated from the logotype, or can be merged as a clean, geometric pictogram with the project name, which is written in *Outfit Bold* and *Outfit Light* to create contrast and clarity. To guarantee consistent and professional use, the brand manual provides multiple variations of the logo – full colour, white, and black – each optimised for visibility on light or dark backgrounds. A “safe area” is defined around the logo to prevent other elements from crowding it, and minimum size recommendations ensure the logo remains legible even when used on small materials such as icons, social media profiles, or partner reports.

Figure 1: The CS-MACH1 project logo

7.1.2 Branding guidelines

The CS-MACH1 brand manual offers a detailed framework to preserve a consistent visual identity across all communication channels. It specifies the primary colour palette – a combination of Space Cadet, Honolulu Blue, Aero, and Maize – complemented by gradients and secondary accent colours such as turquoise and purple when needed. This palette is designed to convey professionalism while remaining vibrant and approachable. The typography guidelines designate *Outfit* as the main institutional font (available in multiple weights) and *Arial* as a web-safe fallback for systems where *Outfit* is not available. Detailed instructions are provided on how to place the CS-MACH1 logo relative to partner logos, how to use it on banners, slides, and reports, and how to adapt it for co-branding situations without losing clarity. The guidelines also define tone of voice—engaging, inclusive, trustworthy, and British English spelling for all communications and clarify the recommended pronunciation of the project name (“Mak uan”). Together, these rules ensure that every output, from press releases to scientific deliverables, speaks with one coherent visual and verbal voice. The brand manual was distributed to the project’s partners as part of the visual identity kit. Full details of the branding guidelines are included in Annexe 1.

7.1.3 Project name and tagline

The project name, **CS-MACH1**, stands for **Marine Citizen Science data Horizon** and carries a symbolic reference to “Mach 1,” the speed of sound – representing acceleration, connectivity, and forward momentum. This metaphor reflects the project’s mission: to be the fastest and most efficient way to connect MCSI, standardise their data, and channel it towards scientific and policy impact. For simplicity the logo tagline was chosen as “Marine Citizen Science Data Horizon”, to immediately visualise what the project is about, but – **“Speeding up Marine**

Data Collaboration” – was chosen as main call to action, reinforcing this message, highlighting the urgency and collaborative nature of the project.

7.1.4 Visual background

The CS-MACH1 visual identity is inspired by the concept of **connection, flow, and data modularity**. Its graphic elements feature abstract, geometric shapes that evoke **data pipelines, nodes, and networks**—a visual metaphor for the project’s mission to harmonise MCSdata flows. Imagery should focus on people, tools, and action, reflecting the participatory and collaborative spirit of the project. The colour scheme places blue at its core, evoking trust and the marine environment, but uses yellow as a powerful secondary highlight to draw attention to key messages and data points. Turquoise and purple may be used as accent colours to give a sense of diversity and innovation, while green, pink, and brown are explicitly discouraged as they were perceived as misaligned with the project’s identity. The resulting visual universe is **modern, approachable, and scientific**, creating an identity that is both serious enough for data integration stakeholders and engaging enough to attract citizen scientists and the general public.

7.1.5 Presentation and document templates

Presentation slides and deliverable templates are designed to ensure coherence and compliance with EU visibility requirements. Each template applies the CS-MACH1 colour palette, uses *Outfit* typography for titles and body text, and integrates modular layouts for agendas, diagrams, and partner logos. A **mandatory EU emblem and funding acknowledgement statement**—“Funded by the European Union”—appears on the cover slide, deliverable cover page, and where appropriate in communications, following the **European Commission’s Horizon Europe logo guidelines** (no alterations to the EU flag, correct minimum size and clear space respected). The CS-MACH1 logo and tagline are placed in accordance with the safe-area rules, ensuring they are clear and prominent. Deliverable templates include space for the deliverable number, work package (WP) reference, submission date, and version control. Slide decks are optimised for readability both on-screen and in hybrid/online events. This ensures that all official outputs—from deliverables and policy briefs to training modules and presentations—are visually consistent, EU-compliant, and immediately recognisable as part of CS-MACH1.

7.2 Newsletters

Newsletters will be used to support the creation of a stakeholders’ community around the project, and to maintain it through time. We will use the newsletter to keep people informed about our project’s news and achievements, building trust using transparent and clear communication which will keep stakeholders engaged. It will feature announcements, news and events from the project and other relevant initiatives, and will highlight successes, key project outcomes and press releases.

The newsletter will be designed using Mailchimp, and delivered via a mailing list in compliance with GDPR. The newsletter design will follow the project’s visual identity guidelines, and will be catchy and quick to read.

In the project's later phases, the newsletter will be an essential tool to share the project's products and results, and to maximise their impact.

One newsletter per project milestone will be delivered. A subscription campaign will be launched before the first newsletter publication, and a subscription button will be present on CS-MACH1 website.

7.3 Project video - documentary

The key results and outcomes of the project will be further captured and promoted through a short documentary (D6.5) produced for the end of the project. This will not only showcase the actions and results of the project, but also be used as an immediate and modern pitch on the value of MCS.

7.4 Press releases

Press releases will be published for each project milestone and sent to relevant media outlets and contacts, including project partners' press offices, to give outreach to project results. The Press Releases will be produced in English. Consortium partners are invited to translate them in their local languages for distribution to local stakeholders.

The press releases will be published on CS-MACH1 website, newsletter/ mailing list and social media, and the consortium partners will support their distribution. According to the content of the press release, it will be distributed to external multipliers (see list below).

Potential media outlets and contacts include:

Science news outlets

- Nature (contact: news@nature.com)
- Science (contact: news@aaas.org)
- New Scientist (contact: news@newscientist.com)
- Science News (contact: editors@sciencenews.org)
- The Science Media Centre (<https://www.sciencemediacentre.org/>)

Environmental news outlets

- Environmental News Network (contact: editor@enn.com)
- The Guardian - Environment (contact: environment@theguardian.com)
- Yale Environment 360 (contact: info@e360.yale.edu)

Ocean and marine science news outlets

- Oceanographic (contact: contact@oceanographicmagazine.com)
- Marine Science Today (contact: info@marinesciencetoday.com)
- Ocean News and Technology (contact: info@oceannews.com)

General news outlets

- BBC News (contact: news.online@bbc.co.uk)
- CNN (contact: newsdesk@CNN.com)
- Reuters (contact: news@thomsonreuters.com)

Local outlets will be targeted when giving outreach to planned meetings and events, leveraging the contacts and relations of Project Partners with their local networks. Press releases may be adapted to suit local media outlets, and translated to local languages as necessary.

7.5 Trainings and training materials

Training activities, events and materials developed by CS-MACH1 will be communicated and disseminated with the tools and channels described in the plan. Training materials and activities will additionally serve as communication tools to widen the recognition of CS-MACH1 and its work to strengthen MCS data processes. Trainings will engage MCSIs and audiences from various target groups, multiplying the reach and impact of the project's messaging.

7.6 European Commission dissemination and exploitation services

CS-MACH1 will explore opportunities to maximise the dissemination and exploitation of its results and outcomes by making use of tools and services provided by the European Commission to Horizon Europe projects. This includes a possible application to use the [Horizon Results Booster](#), potential articles in the DG RTD's [Horizon Magazine](#), and opportunities to optimise dissemination and exploitation via [Open Research Europe](#) and [EU Research & Innovation](#). European Commission platforms, such as the Maritime Forum, will also be used to communicate and disseminate CS-MACH1 and its results.

8. Channels (where)

8.1 Project website

The project website will be launched in M6, following the establishment of the project visual identity, and will be regularly updated. It will serve as a central web-based hub for communication and dissemination of the project results, complementing existing MCS information. The website will provide access to data ingestion portals, training modules, protocols, and resources from WP3, WP4, and WP5 activities and feedback. All content will be free to access and download. Partners will contribute to the content to ensure the website reflects the project's diverse disciplines and areas of focus.

The CS-MACH1 website will be built as a structured, multi-page hub to act as re-directory of the main information needed to build and accelerate a Marine Citizen Science Data Network. The site will open on a **Home** page that gives a concise project overview, highlights news and events, and provides fast links to the network directory, training resources and recent deliverables; an **About** page will explain the CS-MACH1 concept (including the "Mach1" metaphor), objectives, work packages and consortium roles using the EU-preferred terminology (deliverables, WP numbers, DMP, etc.). The **Network** page will host the MCSDN directory – searchable and filterable entries for citizen-science initiatives, contact points, technology providers and partner organisations – while **Training** will present e-learning

modules, video tutorials, downloadable toolkits and schedules for workshops and on-site training. The **Data** page will gather guidance on FAIRness and metadata standards, links to data ingestion portals and EU aggregators (EMODnet, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS), a catalogue of cost-efficient sensors and technical resources for data managers and developers. **Pilot Studies** will describe the co-designed use-cases, operational plans, datasets and lessons learned; **News** will aggregate blog posts, press releases, event pages and a newsletter sign-up; the **Deliverables** section will provide open-access versions of public deliverables, policy briefs and technical reports with versioning, DOIs and links to Zenodo/GitHub for reproducibility; **Impact** will present KPIs, monitoring dashboards and the project roadmap for sustainability and exploitation; and **Contact** will offer sign-up/joining mechanisms for the MCSDN, a contact form, partner acknowledgements and guidance on collaboration. Content and navigation will follow the project's branding and accessibility rules, use British English and EU terminology throughout, include the mandatory EU emblem and funding acknowledgement where required, and ensure GDPR/DMP compliance and long-term availability of resources as described in the project documentation.

8.2 Social media

Social media communication will follow the three campaigns defined in chapter 6, with an initial effort on creating awareness around CS-MACH1 and on building a solid online community.

On social media, we will post regularly about project's updates, events, and products, and we will organise a series of campaigns with different objectives. We will tag project's partners and relevant stakeholders to be sure they know about project's news and updates.

In M4 - M6 we will launch two campaigns, the first one is to present the project's objectives, missions, and values, and the second one is to introduce the project's partners.

In this first phase we will establish our network of stakeholders on both LinkedIn and Instagram, so we will have a critical mass to use in the final phase of the project, to maximise our impact.

We will also take part in international campaigns for relevant months, weeks and days such as:

- International Day of Women and Girls in Science (11th February)
- Citizen science month (April)
- World Ocean Day (8th June)

LinkedIn

LinkedIn has been chosen as CS-MACH1's primary social media platform for outreach and visibility, as it allows for the publication of timely updates and announcements, and a generous 3,000-character limit, which can accommodate posts featuring comprehensive information and storytelling. A direct link to the project account is provided here: [linkedin.com/company/cs-mach1/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/cs-mach1/)

LinkedIn offers various features such as access to professional groups for networking and discussion. Its functionality pushes relevant news and content to specific users based on their

profiles. On LinkedIn, audiences are primarily defined by their role and job position, supporting CS-MACH1 targeted communication towards professionals, researchers, industries, other citizen science and EU projects, and EU and national institutions. This feature is of special value for the CS-MACH1 CDE Plan to engage with stakeholders in relevant fora, and to reach MCSIs that can benefit from the project's outputs. As LinkedIn is widely used for disseminating science, technology and research information, it is useful for monitoring relevant developments in the project landscape. The platform also provides analytics to track the engagement and reach. By maintaining an active presence on LinkedIn, CS-MACH1 can actively communicate on its content territories, foster dialogue, gather feedback, and contribute to broader discussions on marine CS and data related topics, thereby enhancing the project visibility across its target audiences and onboarding stakeholder groups on the project activities. The platform is useful as a professional peer-to-peer platform for generating project credibility and positioning, through additional sharing on personal profiles, appealing to potential partners for legacy actions, and effective promotion.

Instagram

Instagram has been chosen as an additional social media platform for CS-MACH1 as many of our target audiences are active on this platform, including citizen science projects, oceans influencers, students, and in general Gen Z and Millennials. The audience and content present on Instagram allows the project to reach target groups outside of a strictly professional context as is the case with LinkedIn. Instagram allows a more visual and pop style of communication, with audience segmentation based more on the personal interests of users rather than professional roles, enabling a wider potential audience who are potentially interested in MCS activities and data to be reached, while not necessarily engaging with MCSIs in a professional context.

Many citizen science projects and associations (e.g. ECSA, IMPETUS4CS, etc.) have an active Instagram profile, and we aim to build a solid network of stakeholders on this social media.

A direct link to the project account is provided here: [instagram.com/csmach1/](https://www.instagram.com/csmach1/)

YouTube

A CS-MACH1 YouTube channel will primarily serve as a repository for all project-related videos, including interviews, shorts, training materials, and the documentary. Videos will be uploaded to the CS-MACH1 YouTube Channel as and when they are ready for publication. The channel will not be updated on a regular basis, and it is not planned to actively engage with communities on YouTube as is planned for LinkedIn and Instagram.

YouTube videos are easy to share and embed on websites and with other social media platforms (including LinkedIn and Instagram), and they will remain online and accessible after the end of the project.

A direct link to the project account is provided here: <https://www.youtube.com/@CS-MACH1>

8.3 Partner’s websites and social media

The Consortium partners jointly have a robust and well-established presence online via their own websites and social media accounts. As part of its CDE strategy strategy, CS-MACH1 leverages this presence to boost the project's impact and rapidly grow a solid follower base within specialised communities by publishing regular posts on dedicated project social media channels. By tagging Consortium partners in relevant posts, CS-MACH1 messaging will be amplified over a larger audience, therefore increasing the opportunity to engage with more stakeholders. In addition, partners will be encouraged to like, share, and comment on CS-MACH1 social media posts to increase content visibility across their networks.

Table 4. LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube accounts of CS-MACH1 partners and followers (data collected September 2025)

Partner	LinkedIn	Followers	Instagram	Followers	YouTube	Subscribers
CMCC	linkedin.com/company/cmccfoundation	28K	@cmccclimate	6,214	@CMCCvideo	3.4K
SMHI	linkedin.com/company/smhi linkedin.com/showcase/smhi-science-rnd	11K 400	@smhi.se	30.5K	@SMHI	1.98K
ETT	linkedin.com/company/ett-spa	9K	@ettspa	1,970	@ett_spa	569
MARIS	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
OutBe	linkedin.com/company/outbeearth	371	@outbe.earth	3,617	@wild.steps	61
Ifremer	linkedin.com/company/ifremer	98K	@ifremer_officiel	16.4K	@IfremerTV	4.55K
ICM-CSIC	linkedin.com/company/icmcsic linkedin.com/company/embimos-group-citsci	9K 394	@icm.csic @minka.international	5,439 314	@ICM-CSIC @minkasdg	1.28K 17

NOC BODC	linkedin.com/company/british-oceanographic-data-centre	903	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
AUAF	linkedin.com/showcase/ua-acopian-center-for-the-environment	519	n/a	n/a	@auaace	456
ECSA	linkedin.com/company/eucitsci	6K	@ecsa_community	437	@ecsa-europeancitizensscience6914	635
IEEE	linkedin.com/company/ieee-france-section	933	@ieeefrance	113	n/a	n/a
SSBE	linkedin.com/company/seascope-belgium	1K	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
VLIZ	linkedin.com/company/vliz---flanders-marine-institute	10K	@vlizostend	2,427	@VLIZoostende	755
UM	linkedin.com/school/university-of-malta	67K	n/a	n/a	@oceanmalta	103

8.4 Citizen science and data publications, posters and other media

The CS-MACH1 Consortium will seek to disseminate the results of the project via peer-reviewed publications in relevant marine science, citizen science and data management journals, project reports, technical papers, and oral and poster presentations at national, European and international conferences. Dissemination of project results via such publications and presentations will be in compliance with Open Science and FAIR principles.

8.5 CS-MACH1 events and workshops

Various events and workshops will be organised by CS-MACH1 during the project. These will address specific activities and tasks in the project to advance specific objectives. The project events and workshops will additionally serve as CDE events, engaging stakeholders from different target groups and to raise awareness of CS-MACH1 and its outcomes.

Table 5. CS-MACH1 events for the dissemination of of KERs

WP	Type	Descriptions	Target Groups	Relevant KERs	When
WP1	Workshop (MS2)	A hybrid networking workshop to connect to related initiatives, contributing to the GOOS/Odyssey UN Decade Initiatives (CoastPredict, OBPS, EOOS) and engaging communities of practice (e.g., surfing, sailing, diving, fishing)	TG3, TG7, TG8	1	Month 16
WP1	Conference (MS3)	Final conference	ALL	1,4,5	Month 30
WP2	Workshop (MS5)	Networking workshop to connect MCS data actors, focus on best practices, engagement, and networking, involving key actors like device developers and EU data services e.g., EMODnet and EC (e.g., DG MARE). It will feature a session on data/metadata collection to co-design recommendations for data management, observation protocols and best practices (D3.2). This workshop will also boost the visibility of MCS data collection activities across Europe and beyond. WP6 will support the organisation of the workshop with regard to CDE aspects.	TG3, 5, 7, 8	1	Month 9
WP4	Workshop	Four workshops and related e-learning materials will focus on using the MCSDN to provide FAIR data and prepare the data for EMODnet, enhancing environmental monitoring, policy compliance, and ocean literacy	TG3, 7	1,2, 4	
WP4	Training	Boundary organisations and professionals will be trained as MCS	TG4	1,5	

		mediators to facilitate and upscale project objectives beyond its timeline			
WP4 + WP5	Training (MS10)	Two in-person training workshops at pilot sites focusing on the use-case protocols, data management and (if applicable) sensor use	TG3	3,4	Month 23
WP4	MSC policy workshop (MS7)	Explore integrating MCSDN data into policy frameworks like the MSP, MSFD and European Green Deal, and global initiatives like the UN SDGs (Climate Action and Life Below Water)	TG3, TG6, TG7	5	Month 16
WP4	MSC policy workshop (MS8)	Focus on how data from use-cases can aid policy-making	TG3, TG6, TG7	4,5	Month 20
WP4	high level EU event (MS9)	MCSDN functionalities and use-cases showcase	TG6	4,5	Month 26
WP6	Workshop (MS13)	Roadmap workshop	ALL	5	Month 21

8.6 External in-person conferences and events

Various relevant conferences and events organised externally to CS-MACH1 have been identified as potential venues for effective communication and dissemination of CS-MACH1 activities and results, particularly events where target groups are known to congregate and where large audiences relevant to MCS and marine data can be reached. Certain events will be targeted to channel communication efforts. (i) for CS communities, workshops and talks with individualised messages will target key events like dive/boat shows, sailing regattas, fishing competition/equipment shows, Bioblitzes, educational campaigns, community days, to recruit CS data collectors; (ii) for the scientific community, the project impact will be presented at various conferences to demonstrate scientific quality and build trust in CS.

A list of identified relevant events in 2025–2026 that may help raise CS-MACH1’s visibility is included in Annexe 2. The events and potential CS-MACH1 activities there will be reviewed and revised on a regular basis throughout the project according to opportunities that arise, available resources, and the project’s needs.

8.7 Project mailing list

A mailing list will be established for the project, with subscribers joining via the project website. The mailing list will be used to distribute newsletters, press releases and other announcements from the project. The mailing list, open to subscribers from the general public, will be managed and maintained according to GDPR requirements.

9. Tracking and performance monitoring

In order to keep track of all CDE activities across the project, partners share details of any relevant activities they have completed or are planning with the WP6 leads. This is done through a simple internally-shared online table, allowing details and metrics relating to activities to be recorded, including for ad-hoc activities outside those described in this plan, and potential opportunities for joint activities between partners to be identified.

Metrics collected by tracking of CDE activities are used to monitor the performance of CS-MACH1 CDE activities against a set of defined key performance indicators (KPIs). CDE KPIs for CS-MACH1 are detailed in the table below.

Table 6. CS-MACH1 planned actions and activities with corresponding KPI

Planned actions & activities	Relevant to task(s)	KPI	Support Expected Impact	Relevant KER(s)
Dissemination & communication				
Regular content update on project website to ensure project awareness and visibility, supported by online promotion, amplified by cross-partner promotion and social media outreach	T6.2, T6.3, content input from all	20,000 web site visits, 1000 access to resources	3	2
Support stakeholder engagement via communication campaigns, targeted outreach and events	T2.3, T6.3, T6.4	Minimum of 300 participants to the MCSDN	1	1
Capacity building and foster knowledge exchange among stakeholders	T4.1, T4.2, T5.2, T6.4	Minimum 5 workshops	1, 2, 3	4
		Minimum of 5 training resources	1, 2, 3	2, 3, 4
Ensure visibility among stakeholders and wider public, showcase project outcomes and ensure knowledge transfer	T6.4	Minimum 6 conferences presentations, 4 technical papers	3	4

by attending targeted events and producing technical papers				
Participate in targeted outreach activities, ensure direct awareness and engagement of public	T4.1, T6.4	2000 total citizens made aware in person	3	
Highlight key project progress and keep audience well informed of project outcomes	T6.3, content input from all	One press release per milestone		
Regular posts on social media to ensure visibility and awareness	T6.3, content input from all	1500 followers on each social media and one newsletter per milestone		
Showcase key outcomes and engage diverse audience	T6.3, content input from all	8 media products and 1 documentary	3	4
Exploitation				
Enable stakeholders and members of the MCSDN to apply project knowledge and maximise impact	T3.2, T4.1, T6.2, T6.4	Support resources and guidance for the MCSDN	1	1
Support knowledge exchange and enable uptake of knowledge outcome across stakeholder groups	T2.2, T3.2, T4.1, T6.2	Develop a central directory to facilitate the exchange of information such as protocols, trainings and standards	1, 2, 3	2
Provide cost-effective solutions that can enhance the design and operation of marine citizen science initiatives	T2.2, T2.3, T5.2	Collate and share a cost-efficient technologies portfolio	2, 3	2

Monitoring of progress towards meeting the defined KPI targets will guide CDE efforts during the project, supporting the project in ensuring intended impacts are achieved. Monitoring of progress additionally supports overall project monitoring and reporting obligations.

10. Additional plans to support CS-MACH1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

10.1 Widening of outreach towards established partnerships and networks and ensure uptake of project outputs

As part of Task 6.4, actions will be taken to widen CS-MACH1's outreach towards established partnerships and networks relevant to MCS. Leveraging connections made with MCSIs and other stakeholders across the project, activities will aim to expand the MCSDN, promoting engagement of new members. Events will be organised, targeted towards specific communities and networks.

For the scientific community, the project impact will be presented at various conferences to demonstrate scientific quality and build trust in CS, promoting wider uptake and use of CS data, and encouraging engagement with CS-MACH1 and MCSDN activities. With the same aim, existing relevant initiatives of practitioners gathered in the partner's networks will be taken advantage of, such as the ECSA Aquatic Working group.

Activities will aim to engage existing MCSI identified in WP2 to create synergies for communication, education, and training. Partnerships with the EU4Ocean Coalition for Ocean Literacy and the members of its three communities (EU4Ocean Platform, Youth4Ocean Forum, Network of European Blue Schools) will also be pursued to further engage members.

Activities to widen outreach towards established partnerships and networks and ensure uptake of project outputs will be developed as the project progresses, led by Task 6.4. Further details will be provided in version 2 of this CDE Plan (D6.2).

10.2 CS-MACH1 Roadmap

Developed in Task 6.5, the CS-MACH1 Roadmap will be a tool to guide the post-project dissemination, exploitation and legacy. It will outline the project outcomes, incorporating stakeholder feedback on expanding, diversifying, financially funding, and scaling up of the network. It will also assess the integration of MCS data into EMODnet and the European DTO. The Roadmap will consider input from all WPs and establish plans for the MCSDN's post-project implementation, scale up, and sustainability. CDE, both with activities during the project and the post-project MCSDN, will be a key element of the Roadmap and essential to its successful implementation. Further details of CDE aspects of the Roadmap will be elaborated in versions 2 and 3 of this plan.

11. Post-Project Continuity and Legacy

To support continued dissemination and exploitation of project results, ensure sustainability of the MCSDN and to maximise CS-MACH1's legacy, various measures will be taken.

The CS-MACH1 website will remain live and accessible for a period after the project's end to enable continued dissemination and exploitation of key exploitable results and project information, including the archive of project news, newsletters, videos, training materials, and other materials. The website will remain online at least until all directly project-related communication, dissemination and exploitation activities by the project have been completed, and for a minimum of four years after the project ends, in line with obligations detailed in the Grant Agreement.

Additionally to the project website, online open source repositories, such as Zenodo and GitHub, will be used to ensure project outcomes will remain freely available, in line with Open Science and FAIR principles.

Planned or recommended post-project CDE activities will be updated and revised as needed, with further detail to be elaborated in versions 2 and 3 of this CDE Plan.

Annexe 1: Brand manual

Direct link: [CS-MACHI-BrandManualENG-20250901.pdf](#)

<h2>Index</h2> <ul style="list-style-type: none">2. Brand identity and color<ul style="list-style-type: none">3. Logo color4. Pictogram5. Primary palette6. Shades and gradients7. Variants and applications<ul style="list-style-type: none">8. Logo versions9. Applications on various backgrounds16. Use on images18. Geometry, clear space, and dimensions<ul style="list-style-type: none">19. Geometry20. Safe area – horizontal version21. Minimum dimensions22. Typography<ul style="list-style-type: none">23. Logo fonts24. Institutional font25. Secondary font26. Improper use of the logo<ul style="list-style-type: none">27. Unauthorized variations31. Visual and audio identity<ul style="list-style-type: none">32. Audio identity33. Application to charts and tables34. Partner and UE logos	
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Logo color

Version with and without the payoff.

Pictogram

The pictogram must be used where the "CS-MACHI" text does not have enough space to be included (e.g., app icon). Or in charts, tables, maps where the "CS-MACHI" text can be implied.

4

Primary palette

The primary colors are used for all outputs, both online and offline.

Space cadet
 CMYK: 100, 95, 35, 35
 RGB: 35, 37, 79
 #23254F

Honolulu Blue
 CMYK: 85,45,10,0
 RGB: 18, 119, 178
 #1277B2

Aero
 CMYK: 65, 0, 15, 0
 RGB: 73,190,216
 #49BED8

Maize
 CMYK: 15, 0, 85, 0
 RGB: 232, 226, 55
 #E8E237

5

Shades and gradients

The shades of each primary color, from 10% to 90%, must be used as an extension of the primary palette and are mainly applied to tables, charts, icons, illustrations, etc. related to the "CS-MACH1" world.

<p>Space cadet CMYK: 100, 95, 35, 35 RGB: 35, 37, 79 #23254F</p>	
<p>Honolulu Blue CMYK: 85,45,10,0 RGB: 18, 119, 178 #1277B2</p>	
<p>Aero CMYK: 65, 0, 15, 0 RGB: 73,190,216 #49BED8</p>	
<p>Maize CMYK: 15, 0, 85, 0 RGB: 232, 226, 55 #E8E237</p>	

6

Variants and applications

Logo versions

Depending on the background on which the logo is applied, it is preferable to use different versions to make it as legible as possible.

The various cases will be illustrated below.

Logo-color

Logo-White

Logo-Black

“Space Cadet” blue background

On blue backgrounds, logo readability must be ensured.

Therefore, the Logo-White version should be used for blues from 60% to 100% tone.

For tones below 60%, the Logo-Black version must be used.

For the 10% tone, the Logo-color version may also be used.

100%

90%

80%

70%

60%

50%

40%

30%

20%

10%

“Honolulu Blue” background

On “Honolulu Blue” backgrounds, logo readability must be ensured.

Therefore, the Logo-White version should be used for blues from 70% to 100% tone.

For tones below 70%, the Logo-Black version must be used.

For the 10% tone, the Logo-color version may also be used.

100%	
90%	
80%	
70%	
60%	
50%	
40%	
30%	
20%	
10%	

10

“Aero” light blue background

On light blue backgrounds, logo readability must be ensured.

Therefore, the Logo-Black version should always be used across all tones of light blue.

For the 10% tone, the Logo-color version may also be used.

100%	
90%	
80%	
70%	
60%	
50%	
40%	
30%	
20%	
10%	

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“Maize” yellow background

On yellow backgrounds, logo readability must be ensured.

Therefore, the Logo-color version should always be used across all tones of yellow.

100%	
90%	
80%	
70%	
60%	
50%	
40%	
30%	
20%	
10%	

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Black/gray backgrounds

On black and gray backgrounds, logo readability must be ensured.

Therefore, the Logo-White version should be used for blacks from 50% to 100% tone.

For tones below 50%, the Logo-Black version must be used.

For the 10% tone, the Logo-color version may also be used.

100%	
90%	
80%	
70%	
60%	
50%	
40%	
30%	
20%	
10%	

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Dark-colored backgrounds

On dark-colored backgrounds, logo readability must be ensured.

Therefore, the Logo-White version should always be used.

The Logo-color version cannot be used on dark-colored backgrounds.

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CS - MACH1

CS - MACH1

CS - MACH1

CS - MACH1

CS - MACH1

Light-colored backgrounds

On light-colored backgrounds, logo readability must be ensured.

Therefore, the Logo-Black version should always be used.

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CS - MACH1

CS - MACH1

CS - MACH1

CS - MACH1

CS - MACH1

Use on images

When placing the logo on images, the background must be homogeneous and free of excessive details or gradients that compromise readability.

Therefore, depending on the background where it is placed, the Logo-color or Logo-White version should be used.

On images, it is recommended to prioritize the logo version without the payoff.

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Use on images

When placing the logo on images, the background must be homogeneous and free of excessive details or gradients that compromise readability.

Therefore, depending on the background where it is placed, the Logo-color or Logo-White version should be used.

On images, it is recommended to prioritize the logo version without the payoff.

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Geometries

The logo has been placed within a precise rectangle to balance and harmonize the text with the pictogram.

Safe area

A safe area must always be considered around the logo to avoid incorrect placement or interference from other elements in relation to the logo itself.

The safe area on the horizontal or vertical sides is equal to the height of the "CS-MACHI" text.

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Minimum dimensions

These indicate the minimum size allowed for using the logo and are intended to prevent situations of poor legibility of the logo, both in digital and print applications.

The minimum usable size of the logo with payoff is:

The minimum usable size of the horizontal logo without payoff is:

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Logo fonts

The fonts used for the logo are:

- Outfit Bold
- Outfit Light.

Outfit Bold

AaBbCcDdEe123
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 £!@#\$\$%^&*()_+--[{};\,./:"'<>?

Outfit light

AaBbCcDdEe123
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 £!@#\$\$%^&*()_+--[{};\,./:"'<>?

Institutional font

The institutional font of "CS-MACHI" is the **Outfit** family (available on [Google Font](#)).

In all official communications, British English will be used, not American English.

Outfit Thin
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Outfit ExtraLight
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Outfit Light
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Outfit Regular
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Outfit Medium
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Outfit SemiBold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Outfit Bold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Outfit ExtraBold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Outfit Black
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#
 @#1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Secondary font

A secondary font may be used for "CS-MACHI" to ensure compatibility across all platforms and devices, **only if the institutional font cannot be used** (e.g., memos, emails, papers, etc.).

The secondary font is: **Arial** (installed on every device).

Arial Regular
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Arial Bold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Arial Italic Regular
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Arial Italic Bold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%(){}|!?"'@#

Improper use of the logo

Unauthorized variations

To ensure the logo is always recognizable and consistent with the brand image, it is necessary to follow these logo usage guidelines and not modify its colors, fonts, element placement, etc., as in the following examples.

Do not stretch the logo
vertically or horizontally

Do not modify the proportions
or positioning of the text

Unauthorized variations

Do not change the logo's font

Do not change the logo's colors

28

Unauthorized variations

Do not use the logo in outline form

Do not alter, remove, or change individual elements

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Unauthorized variations

Do not apply shadows, gradients, or other effects

Do not place the logo on images or graphics that compromise readability

Audio identity

The "ch" in "Mach" should be pronounced like the "k" sound, similar to the word "mack."
The number "1" should be pronounced as "one."

In all official communications, British English will be used, not American English.

MACH1

“mak uan”

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Application to charts and tables

Charts and tables must align with the visual identity and necessarily follow the same style presented here: solid monochromatic geometric shapes with sharp corners.

Colors must be those of the primary palette or gradients of those colors (see page 6).

Yellow may be used to highlight the most important data since it stands out against the other colors.

The font must be Outfit; if the primary font cannot be used, the secondary Arial font may be applied.

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Partner logos

The logos of CS-MACHI partners may be placed next to the main logo, separated by a vertical line (matching the height of the CS-MACHI logo) and always respecting the clear space distances indicated on page 20. All partner logos must be separated from each other by a vertical line. The same logic must also be applied in the case of a vertical arrangement.

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EU logo

When the EU logo must be included on the same medium (paper, cover, etc.) together with the CS-MACHI logo, the EU emblem must have at least the same prominence in terms of size and visibility as the CS-MACHI logo.

The two logos must never be placed side by side: the EU logo should preferably be positioned on the opposite side of the document or at the bottom of the page, opposite the CS-MACHI logo.

Examples of placement:

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Annexe 2: Identified events for potential CS-MACH1 in-person presence and activities

The below list gives a summary of identified events happening in 2025-2026 to increase CS-MACH1 visibility. This list will be updated regularly during the project with an online version shared between all project partners, allowing tracking of planned and completed CS-MACH1 activities at events.

Event	Short description	Date	Where	Link	Planned or potential CS-MACH1 presence
Mission Ocean Conference	Mission Ocean and Waters EU Presidency Conference	23-24th September, 2025	Nyborg Strand, Denmark	https://event.sdu.dk/misionoceaneu/programme	Yes (AUA)
All-Atlantic Forum	This year's Forum intends to show its commitment to the future of AAORIA and to serve the local communities by continuing to work through ocean science diplomacy to promote a sustainable green and blue transition.	25-26th September, 2025	Brussels, Belgium	https://allatlanticocean.org/all-atlantic-forums/2025-all-atlantic-forum/	Yes (SSBE)
Campus Citizen Science: Artificial Intelligence	How is artificial intelligence changing citizen science?	06 October 2025, 10:00 am - 18:00 pm			
EMODnet Open Conference		25-26 November 2025	Brussels, Belgium	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/events/save-date-emodnet-open-conference-2025	Yes
boot	The largest yacht and	17 - 25	Düsseldorf,	https://www	

Düsseldorf 2026	watersports show in the world	January 2026	Germany	.boot.com/	
OSM2026 (Ocean Sciences Meeting)	Flagship conference for the ocean sciences and the larger ocean-connected community.	22-27 February 2026	Scottish Event Campus, Glasgow, Scotland	https://www.agu.org/ocean-science-s-meeting	Yes
The Austrian Citizen Science Conference	Main event of the year for the citizen science community in Austria and beyond. The third day is a public day, where citizen scientists and the general public are invited to the conference to discover new projects and to get to know project coordinators	24-26 February 2026	Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria	https://oead.at/en/events/detail/2026/02/24/austrian-citizen-science-conference-2026	
ECSA 2026 (European Citizen Science Association)	This year the focus is on exploring the diversity of contexts in which citizen science unfolds – from urban metropolitan hubs to remote northern and southern spaces – and emphasizes its role as a link between centre and periphery	3-6 March 2026	University of Oulu, Finland	https://www.ecsa2026.ngo/	
Oceanology International	Ocean tech and science show that showcases cutting-edge technologies and solutions from across the entire ocean science and technology spectrum. Collaborate, share knowledge, and forge new partnerships with a global network of ocean pioneers.	10-12 March, 2026	London, UK	https://www.oceanologyinternational.com/london/en-gb.html	

BVI Spring Regatta and sailing festival		23-29 March 2026			
EGU 2026	Annual European Geosciences Union General Assembly	3-8 May 2026	Vienna, Austria	https://www.egu26.eu/	
11th EuroGOOS International Conference	European conference for the operational oceanography community, held every 3 years. 2026 edition held back-to-back with EMD 2026 as part of Cyprus' EU Council Presidency Events	18-20 May	Larnaca, Cyprus		
EMD 2026 (European Marine Day)	<p>The EMD is the occasion to pay tribute to "maritime Europe" and put all maritime sectors and activities in the spotlight to help European citizens realise the real outreach and variety of sea-related activities going on in Europe and provoke reflection on the crucial role the seas play in our everyday life.</p> <p>It is the annual event during which Europe's maritime community meet to network, discuss and outline joint action on maritime affairs and sustainable blue economy.</p>	21-22 May 2026	Limassol, Cyprus	https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/governance/european-maritime-day_en	
ICMBO 2026 (International Conference on Marine Biology and		22-23 June 2026	Digital Norway, Oslo		

Oceanography)					
The Tall Ships race	The Tall Ships Races 2026 will offer the perfect opportunity to experience the adventure of a lifetime as it brings together young people from around the world to embark on a voyage of challenge and self-discovery.	Host Ports of Aarhus (24-27 June) Harlingen (3-6 July) Antwerp (11-14 July) Stavanger (22-25 July) Aalborg (30 July -2 August)	See date	https://sailtraininginternational.org/sailtraining/races-regattas/tall-ships-races-2026/	
British classic week	Race with classic yachts, good off the dock atmosphere	20-25 July 2026			
LandSeaLot mid-term conference	Mid-term conference of the LandSeaLot project, including many citizen science activities.	16th September 2026	Brussels, Belgium		
WCMB 2026	'The marine biodiversity insights we need, for the ocean we want'. As the Conference will take place a little over halfway through the UN Ocean Decade, it will provide an excellent opportunity to take stock of ongoing actions and initiatives, but also evaluate what still needs to be tackled by the end of the Decade.	17-20 November 2026	Belgium, Ostend	https://www.wcmb2026.org/	